

TYPES OF CARIES

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Abstract: we examined the types and classes of caries in this article

Key words: Caries, types, class.

Caries (Latin: caries — rot) is a dental disease (see tooth decay). Caries is a common disease, occurring in 95% of the population. Caries is a complex pathological process, in which the tooth tissue is rapidly or slowly eroded and a damaged cavity – cavity is formed on the tooth. Currently, there are several hundred theories about the origin of caries. Many factors play a role in the origin of caries.

Key factors include:

- oral microflora;
- food and nutrition mode;
- the amount of fluoride in water;
- the composition and size of the saliva;
- general condition of my organism;
- extreme effects on my organism;
- endogenous and exogenous factors in the external and internal environment.

There are three different types of caries: anatomical, topographic and clinical. The anatomical classification consists mainly of enamel caries, dentin caries, cement caries. The topographic classification is based on the depth of the disease and is divided into: spot-shaped caries, surface caries, middle caries and deep caries. In terms of clinical course, there are both fast-acting and slow-acting caries. It has white and pigmented spots (Brown to Brown) according to its clinical appearance.

The tests found that caries was white when intensely present, pigmented when slow. Caries's deflection, on the other hand, is of great importance in establishing a cure plan.

Caries pits are divided into Class V based on the Blake classification:

Class I Small and large food fissures of teeth, caries pits located in natural traces;

Caries pits located on contact surfaces of Class II premolars and molars;

Class III cross-sectional edge whole preserved pile and cross-sectional caries bucket on contact surfaces of teeth;

Class IV caries bucket on the contact surface of the pile and incision teeth, where the entire angle of the incision edge is broken;

Class V caries pits located on the neck of the vestibular and oral surfaces of the teeth.

The surface caries is formed by destructive changes in the place of the formed stain caries. The patient complains of short-term pain, in which the chemical effects are formed from sweet, salty, sour. If the caries bucket is located in the neck of the tooth pain can also arise from the thermal effect. When probing, a small defect is detected. The defect settles only on the enamel floor. Electrical sensitivity will be equal to 2-6 MCA. When determining surface caries with hypoplasia, tooth erosion, puncture defect a comparative diagnosis is made.

In the middle caries, the defect will have an average depth of over the enamel, dentin border. In most cases, the patient does not feel pain. In rare cases, the patient complains of short-term pain caused by thermal, mechanical, chemical influences. The examination reveals that there is a caries bucket with an average depth when probing, with softened dentin at the bottom of the bucket. When determining the middle caries, a comparative diagnosis is made with a puncture defect, erosion, chronic periodontitis.

For deep caries, short-term pain is characteristic, which is formed from all types of effects. The pain stops after receiving the affected treatment. It is determined that there is a deep caries Hive, which is dentin softened by examination. When probed, the bottom of the caries bucket is painful, the electrical sensitivity is equal to 2-6 mkA, but in some cases it is equal to 10-12 mkA. In the diagnosis of deep caries, a comparative diagnosis is made with middle caries, acute partial pulpitis and chronic fibrosis pulpitis. With pain generated by mid-caries effects, differs in the depth of the bucket. The occurrence of pain from the pulpits is differentiated by the duration of the pain. In pulpits, electrical sensitivity is equal to 15-20 MCA.

References:

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